

Національна академія наук України
Міністерство освіти і науки України
Державна наукова установа «Київський академічний університет»

«Допущено до захисту»
Завідувач кафедри математики,
доктор фіз.-мат. наук
Вячеслав БОЙКО
«___» травня 2023 р.

Гориславець Дмитро Сергійович

КВАЛІФІКАЦІЙНА РОБОТА

на здобуття освітнього ступеня «магістр»

Спеціальність 122 «Комп'ютерні науки»

**Тема: «Застосування анотованих графів де Брейна
для аналізу даних метагеноміки»**

Засвідчую, що кваліфікаційна робота містить результати власних досліджень. Використання ідей, результатів і текстів інших авторів мають посилання на відповідне джерело. _____ Гориславець Д.С.

Наукові керівники:

Молодший науковий співробітник ІМБГ
НАН України

_____ **Фролова А.О.**

Доктор природничих наук, Федеральна вища
технічна школа Цюриха

_____ **Андре Калес**

Київ — 2023

National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine
State Research Institution «Kyiv Academic University»

«Accepted for defense»

Head of the Department of Mathematics,

D.Sc. **Vyacheslav Boyko**

«___» of May 2023

Dmytro Horyslavets

Master Thesis

Department of Mathematics

Speciality 122 «Computer Science»

**«Applications of annotated de Bruijn graphs for the
analysis of metagenomics data»**

I hereby certify that the thesis contains the results of my own research. The use of the ideas, results and texts of other authors has an appropriate citation.

_____ Dmytro S. Horyslavets

Supervisors:

Junior Research Fellow, IMBG of NASU

_____ **Alina Frolova**

Dr. rer. nat., ETH Zurich, Switzerland

_____ **André Kahles**

Kyiv — 2023

Анотація

Гориславець Д.С., Застосування анотованих графів де Брейна для аналізу даних метагеноміки, Кваліфікаційна робота на здобуття освітнього ступеня «магістр» за спеціальністю 122 Комп'ютерні науки, Київський академічний університет, Київ, 2023, 74 с., 28 джерел.

Метагеноміка набула визнання в якості потужного методу вивчення популяцій мікроорганізмів зібраних у різних середовищах. Однак, аналіз метагеномічних даних ускладнюється тим фактом, що значна частина зразку містить невідому ДНК, пошук якої у референтних базах не дає результату. Таким чином, вивчення та порівняння між собою метагеномічних зразків вимагає розробки спеціальних алгоритмів здатних працювати з неанотованими послідовностями секвенування. Використання графів де Брейна є ефективним способом зберігання великих масивів метагеномічних даних, який також підтримує низку запитів на пошук послідовностей. У цій роботі представлений алгоритм по відновленню послідовностей зчитувань з лічильного графа де Брейна, який дозволяє зберігати закодовані дані без втрат інформації. Алгоритм був розроблений в якості додаткової опції запиту в інструменті “MetaGraph”, який використовує ряд технік для зберігання графа у стисненому форматі, що дозволяє оперувати на дуже великих масштабах даних. Використовуючи переваги лічильних графів де Брейна, дана робота робить внесок у розробку ефективних методів зберігання, індексування та аналізу метагеномічних даних.

АСМ: G.2.2, H.3.3, J.3

Ключові слова: метагеноміка, k -мери, геномні графи, графи де Брейна, лічильні графи де Брейна, алгоритми на графах, Метаграф, вирівнювання послідовностей.

Abstract

Dmytro Horyslavets. Application of annotated de Bruijn graphs for metagenomic data analysis.

Master Thesis, speciality 122 Computer Science. – Kyiv Academic University, Kyiv, 2023, 74 pages, 28 references.

Metagenomics has become a potent method for examining microbial populations across a range of habitats. However, the analysis of metagenomics data presents challenges due to the unannotated nature of a significant portion of the data. De Bruijn graphs have shown promise as an efficient means to store and process large-scale metagenomics datasets. In this study, we propose a novel algorithm for extracting read sequences from a Counting de Bruijn graph within the MetaGraph framework. The MetaGraph framework utilizes compression techniques to store both the graph and annotations, enabling the indexing of global coordinates while operating on a scale of petabase inputs. Our algorithm enables the selection of reads of interest from a lossless Counting de Bruijn graph representation, facilitating comparative analysis of multiple samples without the need to download raw sequences from reference databases. By leveraging the power of Counting de Bruijn graphs and the MetaGraph framework, this research contributes to the development of efficient methods for storing, indexing, and analyzing metagenomics sequencing data.

ACM: G.2.2, H.3.3, J.3

Key words: metagenomics, k -mer sets, genome graphs, de Bruijn graphs, counting de Bruijn graphs, graph traversal, MetaGraph, sequence search.

Contents

Glossary	6
Introduction	7
Chapter 1	
Background	9
1.1. Metagenomics	9
1.2. Fasta/Fastq formats	10
1.3. De Bruijn graphs	12
1.4. Annotated de Bruijn graphs	14
1.5. Counting de Bruijn graphs	15
Chapter 2	
Tools and techniques	17
2.1. DBG-based tools	17
2.2. MetaGraph	18
2.3. BOSS table	19
2.4. RowDiff scheme	25
2.5. Queries against a graph	27
Chapter 3	
Read extraction algorithm	29
3.1. Motivation	29
3.2. Preliminaries	30
3.3. Implementation	30

Chapter 4	
Query experiments	44
4.1. Use case	44
4.2. Small graphs	45
4.3. Huge graphs	48
Results	52
Conclusions	53
References	54
Appendix 1	
Query experiments	58
1.1. Huge graphs	58
Appendix 2	
Algorithm implementation	60
2.1. Path tracing method	60

Glossary

<i>read</i>	Sequence obtained from a single DNA fragment
<i>k-mer</i>	Substring of length k
<i>k-mer count</i>	Number of occurrences of a k -mer in a collection of sequences
<i>k-mer coordinate</i>	Position of a k -mer in a read sequence
<i>DBG</i>	De Bruijn graph
<i>aDBG</i>	Annotated (coloured) de Bruijn graph
<i>cDBG</i>	Counting de Bruijn graph
<i>MetaGraph</i>	Scalable framework that employs the concept of <i>cDBG</i>
<i>BOSS table</i>	Succinct data structure for storing <i>DBG</i>
<i>Annotations</i>	Binary relation between k -mers in a <i>DBG</i> and their labels
<i>Extended annotations</i>	<i>Annotations</i> supplemented with numerical attributes, such as <i>k-mer counts</i> or <i>k-mer coordinates</i>
<i>Annotation matrix</i>	Sparse matrix that stores <i>Annotations</i> of a <i>cDBG</i> .
<i>RowDiff</i>	Compression scheme for encoding numerical attributes of k -mers stored in a sparse matrix
<i>Anchors</i>	Nodes with uncompressed annotations in the <i>RowDiff</i> scheme which serve for the decompression of other annotations
<i>RowDiff path</i>	A path in the <i>DBG</i> that terminates at the nearest descendant anchor node

Introduction

Metagenomics, a rapidly evolving field in the realm of genomics, has revolutionized the study of microbial communities present in various ecosystems. Unlike traditional genomics, which focuses on the genomes of individual organisms, metagenomics involves the extraction and analysis of genetic material directly from a community of organisms. This approach allows researchers to explore the complex interactions and functional potential of entire microbial communities within a given habitat.

However, the analysis of metagenomics data presents several challenges that distinguish it from studying DNA sequences derived from a single genome. One significant hurdle arises from the fact that a considerable portion of metagenomics data remains unannotated, making it predominantly unknown. Furthermore, the absence of well-established guidelines for analyzing large and unannotated datasets compounds the complexity of the task [18].

In recent years, utilizing de Bruijn graphs [10] have gained recognition as a promising approach to address the challenges involved in metagenomics data analysis, driven by the exponential growth of biological data in public repositories [26]. De Bruijn graphs encode the input data with a set of unique overlapping subsequences (k -mers), removing redundancies within and between samples and often providing compression of the data without additional techniques. The graph structure enables the exploration of structural relationships within the dataset and offers a viable solution to manage the expanding volume of metagenomics data while facilitating efficient querying and analysis. Therefore, de Bruijn graphs play a crucial role in making the most of the wealth of genetic information generated and made publicly available through cost-effective DNA sequencing.

The use of de Bruijn graphs in metagenomics addresses the critical need to store vast collections of samples while maintaining the ability to perform

efficient searches. Various compression techniques can be applied to the de Bruijn graph, enabling storage optimisation without sacrificing the ability to query and retrieve information. Meanwhile, the concept of a de Bruijn graph was expanded to the annotated [16] and counting [19] de Bruijn graph. The former extension facilitates distinguishing numerous datasets encoded in a single graph while the latter allows for storing a set of sequences in a graph representation losslessly.

This work proposes a novel algorithm for the read extraction from a Counting de Bruijn graph [19], addressing the fact that efficient read extraction from such graphs has not been implemented yet. The algorithm is developed as an additional query mode within the highly scalable MetaGraph [17] framework. With such an option it is now possible to obtain a set of reads of interest from a dataset that consists of an extensive number of metagenomic samples and is stored in a compressed graph representation.

Chapter 1

Background

1.1. Metagenomics

A typical research pipeline in metagenomics consists of collecting environmental samples, extracting and sequencing DNA, and further analysis of the produced sequences. Modern *Next-Generation Sequencing* (*NGS*) techniques employ the shotgun sequencing method to obtain numerous relatively short DNA segments (25–500 base pairs) [27] called *reads*. Such an approach ensures high coverage, but results in an extensive amount of overlapping sequences. The rapid rise of the *NGS* (also known as *High-Throughput Sequencing*) platforms led to the development of efficient algorithms that operate on produced reads to assemble genomes and align them. The common way to process the reads in multiple types of analysis is to split them into sequences of equal length at first. These subsequences of length k are called *k-mers*, where k is a variable that changes according to the nature of the research. Smaller values of k (21–31) capture shorter sequence patterns and can be more sensitive in detecting similarities or shared regions between sequences. However, smaller k -mers are more prone to occur frequently by chance, leading to lower specificity. On the other hand, larger k values (51–101) capture longer sequence patterns and are more specific in detecting unique regions. Nonetheless, they may miss shorter shared regions or sequences with higher variation.

A distinctive feature of the metagenomics data is the lack of references. Whilst for the organisms with known reference genomes available in public

repositories it is possible to perform their direct comparison to study evolutionary, functional or structural relationships, samples collected from natural communities consist of various organisms, many of which are unculturable and have no reference genomes. For instance, 34.6% of reads collected in a global urban microbiome study conducted by the MetaSub consortium [14] did not map to any reference database.

There have been advances in developing tools that compare unannotated metagenomics datasets with each other [24, 6, 12], which are commonly based on k -mers. However, the exponential growth of the sequencing data accumulating in public repositories [26] necessitates the establishment of optimal methods to store and index massive collections of samples. Compressed k -mer graphs are a promising approach to meet these demands.

1.2. Fasta/Fastq formats

The *fasta* and *fastq* formats are widely used in bioinformatics for representing nucleotide or protein sequence data. These formats provide a standardized way to store and exchange sequence information, including the sequence itself and associated metadata.

The *fasta* format is a simple and widely adopted text-based format for representing sequence data. Each sequence entry in a *fasta* file consists of two parts:

- Header: The header line starts with a “>” symbol and is followed by a unique identifier or description of the sequence.
- Sequence: The sequence data follows the header line and can span multiple lines. It consists of letters representing nucleotides (A, T, G, C) or amino acids (A, R, N, etc.).

Example 1.1. Example *fasta* entry:

```
>sequence_1
ATCGATCGATCGATCG
```

The *fastq* format is an extension of the *fasta* format that includes additional quality score information. It is commonly used for storing sequence reads from high-throughput sequencing platforms. Each *fastq* entry consists of four lines:

- Header: Similar to the *fasta* format, the header line starts with a “@” symbol and contains an identifier or description.
- Sequence: The line following the header contains the actual sequence data.
- Separator: A “+” symbol marks the beginning of the line containing optional additional information. It is typically ignored during processing.
- Quality scores: The line following the separator contains a string of characters representing the quality scores for each base in the sequence. These scores indicate the confidence or reliability of each base call.

Example 1.2. Example *fastq* entry:

```
@read_1
ATCGATCGATCGATCG
+
%++) (%%%) .1**>>
```

The raw sequencing data available in public repositories for analysis is often stored as gzip-compressed *fastq* files. Typically, each such file corresponds to a sample and contains multiple reads which have unique identifiers.

1.3. De Bruijn graphs

The concept of de Bruijn graphs [10] has emerged as a powerful tool in various fields, including bioinformatics, graph theory, and computer science. Originally, de Bruijn graphs were first applied in bioinformatics as a solution for the genome assembly problem. However, they also provide a compact representation of sequences and thus enable efficient analysis of large-scale genomic data.

Definition 1.3. A k -dimensional *de Bruijn graph* (*DBG*) is a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where the set of vertices V consists of all subsequences of length k present in the input sequences. Two vertices are adjacent if they share a substring of length $k - 1$. The start node of a directed edge is the one whose suffix of length $k - 1$ matches the prefix of the same length in the end node.

In practice, each sequence implicitly defines a *DBG* of its overlapping k -mers. Hence, the construction of a *DBG* involves breaking down the input sequence into k -mers and connecting them based on their overlapping relationships. The process can be summarized as follows:

- Split the input sequence into all possible k -mers.
- Create a node in the *DBG* for each distinct $(k - 1)$ -mer.
- For each k -mer occurrence in the sequence, create a directed edge between the $(k - 1)$ -mer prefix node and the $(k - 1)$ -mer suffix node.

The resulting *DBG* represents the relationships between k -mers in the input sequence, capturing the local structure and allowing for subsequent analysis and exploration. This graph-based representation treats a read sequence as a path in a graph consisting of consecutive k -mers, enabling various analyses and algorithms for genome assembly, sequence alignment, variant calling, and metagenomics, among others. By leveraging the graph structure, these applications can efficiently explore and extract valuable

information from the sequence data. For example, in genome assembly, the *DBG* can be used to reconstruct the original genome sequence by traversing the graph paths that correspond to different genomic regions. When it comes to sequence alignment, the graph can help identify similarities and differences between sequences by aligning paths or finding common patterns. In the realm of metagenomics, *DBG* allows for the characterization of complex microbial communities by analyzing the connections and abundances of different k -mers in the graph.

Example 1.4. Figure 1.1 depicts a visual representation of the graph, illustrating the set of vertices $V = \{\text{TTA}, \text{TAC}, \text{ACG}, \text{CGA}, \text{GAC}, \text{GAA}, \text{AAT}, \text{ATT}, \text{TAG}\}$, which are derived from splitting the sequences TTACGACG and CGAATTAG into 3-mers.

Figure 1.1. A joint de Bruijn graph with $k = 3$, constructed from two sequences: TTACGACG and CGAATTAG.

However, when attempting to encode multiple sequences in a single *DBG*, certain limitations appear. One key challenge is the potential loss of information regarding the origin and identity of individual sequences. When multiple sequences are merged into a single graph, it becomes hard or even impossible to distinguish which specific sequence a given path or node corresponds to. As Figure 1.1 shows, without additional metadata, a

single *DBG* built from several sequences can only provide information about all the unique k -mers present in the input.

Thus, several generalisations have been proposed to address the inherent constraints associated with the concept of *DBG*.

1.4. Annotated de Bruijn graphs

When storing miscellaneous sequencing data consisting of multiple samples, it is often necessary to retain information about the samples of origin for each read to perform more flexible analyses. For example, in a study focusing on the genetic variation within a single organism, researchers can utilize sample labels to identify specific genetic variants present in different samples. By examining the distribution and frequency of these variants, they can gain insights into the genetic diversity within the organism and study how different variants may be associated with specific traits or phenotypes. In another scenario, researchers studying microbial communities in different environmental samples can use sample labels to track the abundance and distribution of specific microbial species or functional genes. This allows for comparisons between samples from various geographical locations or environmental conditions, revealing how these factors influence the composition and functional potential of microbial communities. A possible solution in the form of keeping a separate graph for each sample is highly inefficient. Instead, this can be achieved by introducing a binary relation between the k -mers that correspond to the nodes of a *DBG* and labels of their samples of origin. These supplementary metadata is called *annotations* and may be stored either incorporated in the graph or as a separate data structure. A visually intuitive representation is achieved by using coloured nodes, where each colour corresponds to a specific sample. Such construction is called *annotated* (or *coloured*) *de Bruijn graph* and was proposed by Iqbal *et al.* (2012) [16] as a way to encompass sequences from various sources into a unified graph.

Figure 1.2. Annotated de Bruijn graph with $k = 3$, constructed from two sequences: TTACGACG (labelled as green) and CGAATTAG (labelled as red).

Definition 1.5. An annotated (coloured) de Bruijn graph (*aDBG*) is a *DBG* supplemented with colours assigned to each node which represent different samples.

Example 1.6. The sequences TTACGACG and CGAATTAG from Example 1.4 are assigned the colours red and green, respectively, resulting in the *aDBG* shown in Figure 1.2.

1.5. Counting de Bruijn graphs

The *aDBG* described in the previous section enables the distinction of k -mers originating from different sources. However, it is important to note that the precise order of k -mers in the input sequences may be lost. This limitation becomes evident when the resulting graph contains cycles consisting of nodes of the same colour. In such cases, relying solely on colours becomes insufficient for the accurate reconstruction of the original sequences.

To alleviate this issue, Karasikov *et. al* (2022) [19] proposed *Counting de Bruijn graphs (cDBG)*, an extension of *aDBG* that enhances each k -mer-label relation with additional numerical attributes. These attributes, as suggested by the authors, can include k -mer counts, which represent the

number of occurrences of a k -mer in a sample, or k -mer coordinates that describe the positions of a k -mer in the input sequences. Such graph annotations are called *extended*. Importantly, when indexing k -mer coordinates, the resulting representation preserves the entirety of the input sequences without any loss of information.

Figure 1.3. *Counting de Bruijn graph* with $k = 3$, constructed from two sequences: TTACGACG (labelled as green) and CGAATTAG (labelled as red). The numerical attributes written in curly braces indicate the positions of the k -mers in their respective sequences.

Definition 1.7. A *Counting de Bruijn graph* (*cDBG*) is an *aDBG* with each k -mer-label relation supplemented with additional numerical attributes.

Conceptually, a *cDBG* consists of a *DBG* index and *extended annotations*, which are represented as a sparse matrix. Storing graph metadata in the form of a matrix enables the application of compression techniques to reduce the memory footprint.

Example 1.8. For the *aDBG* depicted in Figure 1.2, preserving the coordinates of the k -mers from the underlying sequences in the form of a *cDBG* yields a graph visualised in Figure 1.3.

Chapter 2

Tools and techniques

2.1. DBG-based tools

In the past decade, there has been a significant rise in the development of de Bruijn graph-based tools to address the growing demand for efficient DNA sequence alignment [17, 5, 22, 4, 25, 23]. These tools typically involve the construction of a *DBG* index using reference sequences and employ a seed-and-extend approach to align query sequences to the graph.

However, it is important to note that only a small subset of these tools incorporate global reference genome coordinates, which provide information about the position of an input sequence within a genome [19]. Furthermore, the tools that do utilize genome coordinates are primarily designed for efficient querying, and as a result, they may encounter difficulties when dealing with extremely large datasets [19]. An instrument designed to provide the best balance between the memory usage of a graph index and querying time is called *MetaGraph* [17]. This tool makes use of the *cDBG* concept described in Section 1.5, which allows for encompassing sequencing data into the index without loss of information. *MetaGraph* exploits multiple sophisticated compression techniques [18, 13] to store the *annotations matrix* in a space-efficient manner while maintaining efficient querying capabilities. This makes the tool highly scalable and capable of handling petabytes of sequencing data.

For these reasons, in this work, we will focus on the *MetaGraph* framework as the foundation for developing *DBG*-based algorithms meant to operate on the vast collections of metagenomics samples.

2.2. MetaGraph

Metagraph offers a variety of options to store both the graph and annotations of a *cDBG* [17]. Specifically, the available formats for the graph index are:

- The succinct BOSS table [8] representation (*SuccinctDBG*).
- Compressed indicator vector of the k -mer presence (*BitmapDBG*).
- A hash-table of k -mers (*HashDBG*).

Similarly to the graph, *MetaGraph* provides several options for storing the annotation matrix. Depending on specific requirements, users can choose from formats such as *RowCompressed*, *ColumnCompressed*, *Multi-BRWT* [18], and other available options.

Importantly, aside from applying techniques for compressing arbitrary sparse matrices, the topology of the underlying sequencing data is leveraged in *Metagraph* to achieve even higher compression performance. The framework adopts a technique called *RowDiff* [13] which utilizes similarities of adjacent k -mers in the graph. The combination of multiple compression methods allows *MetaGraph* to achieve compression ratios of up to 1,000 compared to the already compressed raw data [17].

The annotations of the k -mers in a *cDBG* as described in Section 1.5 can be of two types: k -mer counts and k -mer coordinates. Onwards we will consider only the k -mer coordinates as additional metadata for a *cDBG* as this construction ensures no loss of information. This makes it possible to develop the algorithm for reconstructing the original sequences from a *cDBG* index which is the ultimate goal of this work.

Also, this study aims to focus specifically on the *SuccinctDBG* format for storing the graph index, as it has demonstrated the highest compression rate compared to other representations [17]. However, it's worth noting that the algorithm proposed in this work is valid for all the aforementioned

graph structures. This adaptability is possible due to the modular structure of *MetaGraph*, which allows for the convenient extension of the tool’s API.

In the next sections, we will describe the key aspects of the compression techniques which will allow us to formulate the motivation behind this work.

2.3. BOSS table

Succinct data structures are representations of data that aim to achieve efficient storage and retrieval while minimizing space usage. These structures have gained prominence in various fields, including bioinformatics, where large-scale genomic data analysis poses significant challenges.

Definition 2.1. If N is the information-theoretical number of bits needed to store some data, a representation of this data that takes $N + o(N)$ bits of space is called *succinct*.

Succinct representation techniques often rely on the construction of succinct indexable dictionaries, also referred to as *rank/select dictionaries*. These structures are designed to store a subset of elements from a universe, such as the k -mers present in a *DBG*. Typically, this is achieved using bit vectors and two fundamental operations: $\text{rank}_c(i)$ which determines the number of occurrences of the element c up to position i and $\text{select}_c(i)$ which identifies the position of the i^{th} occurrence of c . When operating on bit vectors, $c = 1$, and is often omitted. The most well-known examples of such structures include binary trees, multisets and suffix trees.

Example 2.2. For the bit vector 00101101, $\text{rank}(4) = 2$, $\text{select}(2) = 4$ (0-based indexing).

Example 2.3. For the sequence TATCGA, $\text{rank}_A(4) = 1$, $\text{select}_A(2) = 5$ (0-based indexing).

A succinct representation of a *DBG* was proposed by Bowe *et al.* (2012) [8]. In the proposed encoding scheme, a graph with m edges needs $4m + o(m)$ bi-

ts. Also, various operations, such as getting the outdegree of a node or following the outgoing edge are supported with the use of rank / select operations.

Eventually, the representation was named BOSS which is an abbreviation that consists of the first letters of the authors' surnames. Now it is commonly referred to as the BOSS table.

To gain a better understanding of the construction process of the BOSS table, let us consider an illustrative example from the author's personal blog [7].

Example 2.4. *DBG* with $k = 3$ built from the sequence TACGACGTCGACT results in the following visualization.

Figure 2.1. *De Bruijn graph* from Example 2.4 [7].

In this graph representation, the edges are assigned labels, too. Specifically, for each pair of adjacent nodes $u \rightarrow v$, the edge is labelled with a symbol that corresponds to the last symbol in the end node v .

After adding padding that will make each node have at least one incoming and outgoing edge the graph takes the following form.

Figure 2.2. *De Bruijn graph* with paddings denoted by symbol \$ [7].

At this point, each node's k -mer label is totally defined by its k previous edges in the graph. Further, all $\langle \text{node}, \text{outgoing edge} \rangle$ pairs are sorted in the colexicographic order of the nodes (i.e. based on the reverse of the node label). The obtained table with the edge labels array denoted by W is shown in Figure 2.3.

<i>Node</i>	<i>W</i>
\$ \$ \$	T
C G A	C
\$ T A	C
G A C	G
G A C	T
T A C	G-
G T C	G
A C G	A
A C G	T
T C G	A-
\$ \$ T	A
A C T	\$
C G T	C

Figure 2.3. The table of the node-edge labels sorted in the colex order of the underlying k -mers [7].

An edge label in W is supplemented with a minus sign if there is already another edge with the same label assigned to a node sharing the same suffix of

length $k - 1$. This approach ensures unambiguous navigation along incoming edges when multiple edges share the same label. For instance, the node ACG has two incoming edges labelled with G. As the edge that corresponds to the node GAC appears before the one that correspond to the node TAC in the sorted table, the latter is marked with the minus sign.

After that, the bit vector L (*last*) is introduced to tag the unique k -mers in the nodes. This vector facilitates indexing nodes with the help of the select operation.

L	$Node$	W
1	\$ \$ \$	T
1	C G A	C
1	\$ T A	C
0	G A C	G
1	G A C	T
1	T A C	G-
1	G T C	G
0	A C G	A
1	A C G	T
1	T C G	A-
1	\$ \$ T	A
1	A C T	\$
1	C G T	C

Figure 2.4. The vector L (*last*) marks unique nodes with ones. For example, there are two outgoing edges from the node ACG: one labelled with A and another with T. In the table, only the latter has the set bit in L [7].

Finally, the offset structure F is added to eliminate the need to store the original node labels (Figure 2.5).

The resulting representation comprises the array of edge labels W , the bit vector L , and the offset structure F , and does not store labels of the nodes explicitly.

Figure 2.5. Array F stores the start positions of the last symbols in the node labels. Since the labels are sorted and each node is determined by its k incoming edges, the original nodes' labels can be replaced with F in the final representation [7].

Thus, formally, the BOSS table representation of a DBG with n vertices and m edges, built from the sequence T of length N on alphabet \mathcal{A} consists of three components:

- A string W of length m where each symbol is from $\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{A}^-$.
- A string $last$ of length m on the binary alphabet $\{0, 1\}$.
- An offset structure F of length $\sigma = |\mathcal{A}|$.

Where \mathcal{A}^- is defined as any set of size $|\mathcal{A}|$ such that $\mathcal{A}^- \cap \mathcal{A} = \emptyset$ [8].

Since in the BOSS table elements are sorted and each node can be determined by its predecessor edges, the relative positions of the node labels are the same as the positions of the edge labels (Figure 2.6).

This construction enables essential navigation operations in the graph. For instance, by utilizing the previously defined functions `rank` and `select`, the `forward(i)` and `backward(i)` operations can be implemented. The `forward(i)` operation returns the index of the last edge of the node pointed to by edge i , while the `backward(i)` operation returns the index of the first edge that exits

the node pointed to by edge i . Both of these operations have a constant-time complexity [8]. Furthermore, they serve as a foundation for more complex operations, such as determining the outdegree of a node ($\text{outdegree}(v)$) or traversing the edge with a specific label ($\text{outgoing}(v, c)$) [8]. Figure 2.7 shows the implementation of the forward operation using the functions rank and select on the arrays F , W and last .

Figure 2.6. The relative ordering of the nodes' labels is preserved in the vector W [7].

The navigational interface of the BOSS table is implemented in *MetaGraph*, allowing for functionalities such as mapping raw sequences to node indexes, traversing the edges in both directions, spelling paths of node indexes back to sequences and more. The versatile API of the framework facilitates the development of the *DBG*-based algorithms that employ the concept of the BOSS table.

Figure 2.7. Operation $forward(i)$ on a BOSS table implemented using rank and select functions. The index of the last edge of a successor for the node with index 2 (0-based) is obtained as follows: i) Get the rank of the current edge label C in W . ii) Determine the start position of the nodes with the last symbol C using array F . iii) Find the rank to base. iv) Select the relatively positioned node by combining rank to base and rank of the current edge label to retrieve the result index, which in this example is 5 [7].

2.4. RowDiff scheme

As described in Sections 1.5 and 2.2, a *cDBG* index consists of the graph itself and its numerical metadata called annotations. Not only the graph but the corresponding annotations are stored in a compressed representation within the *MetaGraph* framework.

In order to have the ability to operate on extensive collections of samples, up to the petabase scale, *MetaGraph* makes use of both the general matrix compression techniques, such as *Multi-BRWT* [18], and the method that takes advantage of the similarities of the neighbouring k -mers in the sequences determining the graph and is called *RowDiff* [13].

The *RowDiff* compression scheme was proposed by Danciu *et al.* (2021) [13] as a sparsification method for the annotations matrix where the rows

typically represent the nodes of the corresponding *DBG*. The main idea behind the *RowDiff* technique is to encode each node’s annotations with their difference with respect to an adjacent node. Specifically, for each node, the *RowDiff* successor is defined as its adjacent k -mer with the highest lexicographic value. Further, the rows in the annotations matrix are replaced with the delta compared to their *RowDiff* successors. The delta operation varies depending on the type of stored annotations. That is, for binary annotations comprising only k -mer labels (described in Section 1.4) the delta can be specified as the component-wise XOR operation [13].

Importantly, the *RowDiff* transformation is revertible which is achieved by keeping some nodes’ annotations uncompressed. These nodes are called *anchors* and serve for the decompression of the annotations of other nodes. To reconstruct the original annotations for a node, one must follow the edges until the *anchor* node is met with subsequent application of the inverse delta operation to the nodes along the obtained path which is called the *RowDiff path* [13].

The *anchors* are assigned during the *RowDiff* construction which involves the traversal of a graph starting from all the sink nodes, followed by traversal starting from the source nodes and traversal of the unvisited forks. During the traversal, a node is marked as an *anchor* at every M -th step. Parameter M is tuneable and is needed to limit the maximum length of the *RowDiff paths* in a graph [13].

The *RowDiff* technique was revised and optimized by Karasikov *et al.* (2022) [19]. In this work [19], among other improvements, the delta operation involved in the *RowDiff* compression and decompression was generalized to arbitrary sets of numerical annotations, including the *k-mer counts* and *k-mer coordinates* mentioned in Section 1.5.

Example 2.5. Figure 2.8 [19, Figure 3B] illustrates the *RowDiff* transformation applied to the annotations which contain coordinates of the k -mers extracted from sequence ACTAGCTAGCTAG ($k = 3$). The *anchors*

are marked red. The delta operation is defined as a symmetric set difference between the row's coordinates increased by 1 and its *RowDiff* successor. For instance, when applied to the node AGC: $(\{4, 8\} \oplus 1) \Delta \{5, 9\} = \{\}$, which results in a sparsified representation.

Figure 2.8. *cDBG* with $k = 3$ constructed from sequence ACTAGCTAGCTAG with the *RowDiff* scheme applied to the annotations which store k -mer coordinates. The delta operation involves calculating the symmetric set difference which is defined as $A \Delta B := (A \cup B) \setminus (A \cap B)$ [19, Figure 3B].

The inverse of the compression operation is easily derived based on the basic properties of the symmetric set difference.

2.5. Queries against a graph

DBG-based tools serve the main purpose of enabling sequence alignment, a fundamental problem in bioinformatics for identifying similarities between biological sequences. The common approach involves using the seed-chain-extend method. Seeds, short similarity regions, act as anchor points, and chain extension gradually expands the alignment by considering local similarities and employing scoring models. This approach balances speed and accuracy, making it suitable for aligning large-scale genomic sequences, thanks to the *DBG* index.

MetaGraph utilizes the seed-chain-extend approach enhanced with some heuristics [17, 19] for sequence alignment against a *cDBG* index (Figure 2.9).

Figure 2.9. The *MetaGraph* framework leverages the constructed *cDBG* index to facilitate various types of sequence searches. It enables either searching for samples that contain specific *k*-mers from the input sequence or aligning sequences against the graph, yielding matching paths and their associated labels [2].

In some types of analyses, the use of *cDBG* annotations can increase the accuracy of sequence search. However, since the annotations are stored in a compressed format, their decompression is necessary. Yet, decompressing the entire set of annotations for large-scale graphs is impractical. Therefore, when designing algorithms for *cDBG* operations, it is essential to consider implementing partial decompression of the annotations.

The *MetaGraph* framework provides a scalable and extensible API which comprises methods both for navigation in the graph and manipulations with annotations matrix, including decompression of the annotations for a set of nodes. This interface can be used as a base for developing new *cDBG*-based algorithms.

Chapter 3

Read extraction algorithm

3.1. Motivation

The techniques that *MetaGraph* employs for storing the graph and annotations of a *cDBG* (described in Sections 2.3, 2.4) allow it to be seen not only as an index for sequence searching but as a full-fledged data repository intended to store millions of samples. While the BOSS table [8] format enables efficient navigation in a graph, the generalized *RowDiff* [13, 19] scheme used to store k -mer coordinates ensures no loss of the stored data information.

This generates a need for the option to retrieve the original read sequences which may be used for subsequent analyses. The possibility of such a graph query would distinguish the *MetaGraph* tool from existing counterparts, which allow aligning sequences to the graph, but not reconstructing the original reads.

For this reason, the corresponding algorithm for the read extraction from a *cDBG* was developed in this work. It utilizes the *MetaGraph* API to operate on a *cDBG* stored in the compressed representation, enabling reconstruction of the reads that overlap with a given query. The existence of such an algorithm facilitates the global sequence discovery problem when the objective is to retrieve all the reads of interest, for example, to perform a comparative analysis across multiple samples. By providing the alternative to raw sequence search in reference databases, the proposed algorithm naturally inherits the benefits of *cDBGs* and complements the existing set of query options available in *MetaGraph*.

3.2. Preliminaries

Before we introduce the algorithm, the key aspects of the *cDBG* construction must be mentioned. The basic construction of a *cDBG* index in *MetaGraph* consists of two steps:

- Build a plain graph from *fasta/fastq* files.
- Annotate the *k*-mers in a graph using the input *fasta/fastq* files.

While specifying parameters during the construction steps of the *cDBG* index, one crucial aspect is the assignment of labels and coordinates to the *k*-mers. During the annotations stage, *MetaGraph* provides two options: using the filenames of sample files (referred to as the `--anno-filename` flag) or using the headers of the underlying read sequences stored in the *fasta/fastq* files (referred to as the `--anno-header` flag) as labels.

The first option creates a separate column in the annotations matrix for each read sequence present in the input sample files, enabling the *k*-mers to have coordinates relative to each read sequence individually. In contrast, the latter representation assigns a single label with contiguous coordinates to the *k*-mers from all the reads in a single sample. For example, the first *k*-mer of the second read in a sample will have the coordinate $c + 1$, where c is the coordinate of the last *k*-mer in the first read, and so on.

Although the proposed read extraction algorithm can handle both options, this work will focus on utilizing the `--anno-filename` representation. This choice is driven by the higher compression rate provided by this representation, making it particularly suitable for storing large collections of samples.

3.3. Implementation

The algorithm for reconstructing the reads forming the *cDBG* makes use of the fact that the sequencing data is stored losslessly when the annotation

matrix contains k -mer coordinates. The main idea behind the algorithm is to obtain a set of nodes from a graph with their decompressed annotations sufficient to retrieve paths in the graph that will be used to reconstruct the read sequences.

As the *cDBG* may contain petabytes of data, the key principle is to traverse only a subgraph and decompress only a portion of annotations. At the same time, performing a check on whether the graph has to be traversed more at each step of the traversal is highly inefficient due to the vast nature of the stored annotations. Thus, the more feasible way to obtain the needed amount of nodes and their original annotations involves the traversal of the graph in parts (batches) with subsequent decompression of the annotations of the nodes in a batch.

The entry point of the query execution is the *fasta* file with the query sequences. The *fasta* file is parsed to extract the sequences and their headers. Those sequences can be processed in parallel as *MetaGraph* includes the Thread Pool implementation.

Subsequently, when a query sequence is passed as an input to the read extraction method, it is split into k -mers which are further mapped to the corresponding indexes of nodes in the graph along with the indexes of rows in the annotations matrix. The corresponding methods are available as the existing *MetaGraph* functionality and utilize the BOSS table for the mapping step. After that, each row index is passed to the paths tracing method (Algorithm 2) which returns all paths in the graph that are consistent in coordinates (and thus represent the read sequences) which contain the passed k -mer corresponding to the row index. This method forms the main part of the algorithm developed in the context of this work. The obtained paths in the graph consisting of the node indexes and corresponding sample labels are spelled into sequences with the help of the available *MetaGraph* method called `spell_paths(...)`.

The final result is returned in the form of the *TSV* output with 6 columns:

1. Query id.
2. Query label (header from the *fasta* file).
3. Extracted read sequence.
4. Label of the sample containing extracted read.
5. Coordinate of the query k -mer in the query sequence.
6. Coordinate of the k -mer in the extracted read sequence.

Algorithm 1 displays the process of mapping the sequence to the node and row indexes, calling the paths tracing method and spelling the resulting paths.

Algorithm 1 Read Extraction

```

1: function GETOVERLAPPINGREADS(sequence)
2:   nodes  $\leftarrow$  MAPTONODES(sequence)  $\triangleright$  MetaGraph API
3:   rows  $\leftarrow$  GRAPHTOANNOTATIONSINDEX(NODES)  $\triangleright$  MetaGraph API
4:   vector result  $\leftarrow$  an empty vector
5:   for row in rows do
6:     traced_paths  $\leftarrow$  GETTRACESWITHROW(row)
7:     spelled_sequences  $\leftarrow$  SPELLPATHS(traced_paths)  $\triangleright$  MetaGraph API
8:     result.PUSHBACK(spelled_sequences)
9:   end for
10:  return result
11: end function

```

The main ideas of the GETTRACESWITHROW(...) method are described in Algorithm 2. Firstly, when passed an input row index, the annotations for that row are decompressed. The decompressed annotations for a single row are returned in the form of a vector of pairs $\langle Column, Tuple \rangle$, where *Column* is the index of the column in the annotations matrix which corresponds to the sample label and *Tuple* is a vector of k -mer coordinates.

The decompressed annotations of the input row are used as the initial ends of reads. Specifically, each coordinate that does not have a continuation

is marked as the current end of some read. These temporary ends of reads can be seen as seeds which will be updated during the graph traversal.

Further, the graph is traversed forwards using breadth-first-search (BFS) as the maximum node degree in a *DBG* is small and finite (e.g., for nucleotide sequences, there are 4 possible labels for an edge). Importantly, this is done in batches. Specifically, at each step of the traversal, the nodes traversed with the BFS are converted to the row indexes and collected into the batch (Algorithm 2, line 18). In turn, the maximum batch size is a tuneable parameter that is specified before the query. As the size of the current batch exceeds the maximum batch size, the traversal stops (line 20). After that, the annotations for the batch of rows are decompressed using the *MetaGraph* API method `GETROWTUPLES(...)` (line 24). This method is designed to decompress the annotations for the vector of rows and keeps the results of decompression for previous nodes in the vector while processing the next ones. Such an approach allows for building shorter *RowDiff* paths (described in Section 2.4) which may end not only with the *anchor* nodes but with the nodes which have their annotations already decompressed.

After that, the decompressed annotations of the current batch of rows are used to collect the newly visited nodes and their coordinates into the set of all traversed nodes (line 26). The next step involves updating the ends of the reads by checking the coordinates increase in the set of all traversed nodes (line 28). That is, for each read end, the set of traversed nodes is checked for the coordinate increase relative to the coordinate of the read end. If there is an increase, then the read end coordinate must be updated with the bigger one.

Finally, for each end of the read, the outgoing adjacent nodes are examined for increased coordinates (line 30). The successors of the current read ends which have increased coordinates represent the continuations of the underlying reads which means that the graph has to be traversed more. Conversely, if the current read end coordinate does not have a continuation in any of the

corresponding successor nodes, then it marks the true end of the read. The traversal continues until all the reads' ends have no continuations in their successor nodes.

Since the *DBG* is a directed graph, the forward traversal is followed by the backward traversal (line 40) to visit all the nodes forming the read sequences. The backward traversal is done in the same way as the forwards, with the only difference that instead of output nodes, incoming nodes are examined (line 47) and instead of the coordinates' increase we look for the coordinates' decrease for the starts of the reads (line 56).

Upon the forward and backward traversal of the graph, the true ends and starts of the reads are obtained respectively. In combination with the set of traversed nodes and their coordinates, they allow to correctly reconstruct the read sequences by acting as the delimiters (line 64).

The steps of Algorithm 2 called in lines 4, 19, 28 and 30 are described as functions in Algorithms 3, 4, 5, and 6, respectively. Function `FINDENDS(...)` (Algorithm 3) returns a map of column indexes to set of coordinates that have no continuations among the annotations of the query k -mer. During the local graph traversal procedure `ENQUEUEADJACENTOUTGOINGNODES(...)` (Algorithm 4) is used to call the outgoing k -mers and add them to queue. To update the ends of reads using the newly traversed nodes and their coordinates, function `UPDATEENDS(...)` (Algorithm 5) is used. This function seeks the coordinate increase consistent with a path in a graph to update old ends of reads with their continuations. Lastly, to check if there is a need to traverse the graph more, function `CHECKIFTRAVERSEMOREFORWARD(...)` (Algorithm 6) is utilized. During the check if the further traversal is required, the successors of the ends of reads are examined for the presence of coordinate increase. The ends that do not have a continuation in any successor are added to the separate set of the true read ends.

The analogues of the above functions for the backward traversal called in

lines 35, 47, 56 and 58 use the same approaches, with the difference that the incoming edges are called and the coordinate decrease is inspected.

In practice, Algorithm 2 is enhanced with several improvements:

- Instead of using the existing `GETROWTUPLES(...)` method available in *MetaGraph* to decompress the annotations for the row or batch of rows, a modification to this method was implemented. The modified method supports restricting the decompression to the set of user-specified sample labels. This is particularly useful when extracting reads from a huge graph which contains a lot of samples. In that case, if there is a need to reconstruct the reads only for the specific set of samples stored in a *cDBG* index, one can pass the titles of the samples and the modified decompression method will consider only the relevant columns in the annotations matrix. This adjustment accelerates the execution of the algorithm and prevents the need to load all columns of the annotation matrix into RAM.
- The algorithm keeps the reads reconstructed for the previous k -mers in the sequence when processing the next ones. By taking advantage of the fact that adjacent k -mers in the input sequence often belong to the same reads, this improvement increases execution speed by an order of magnitude.
- During the process of updating reads' ends, the continuations of the discovered reads are collected into a new queue, replacing the old queue. This guarantees starting the traversal of the next batch from the nodes which are ensured to be relevant. As the traversal is being performed on a plain graph (without knowing the annotations of the newly visited nodes), this improvement speeds up the traversal almost by a factor of 10.
- In a single traversal step, the check of whether further traversal of the graph is necessary is followed by the clean-up procedure. The traversed

nodes with coordinates that exceed the maximum read end coordinate are erased from the set of all traversed nodes. Empirically, adding this step resulted in less RAM consumption and slightly reduced execution time.

The implementation of Algorithm 2 as the C++ method within the *MetaGraph* framework is available in Appendix 2.1. The complete implementation can be found in the fork of *MetaGraph*:

<https://github.com/d-goryslavets/metagraph>.

Example 3.1. Consider a *cDBG* with $k = 4$ built from two sequences: AATGCTGCTAATGCTT (labelled as red) and CAATGCTT (labelled as blue). The annotations of the *cDBG* index contain the coordinates of the k -mers from each sequence. Additionally, assume that both of the sequences belong to the same sample. This implies that the coordinate of the first k -mer CAAT in the blue-labelled sequence is 13 (since the red-labelled sequence contains 13 k -mers and the indexing is 0-based).

Let $maxBatchSize = 3$ and $query = CAAT$. The resulting graph and query sequence mapped to the input node are shown in Figure 3.1i.

After the decompression of the annotations of the input node (Figure 3.1ii), the coordinates of the k -mer CAAT are initialized as starts and ends of the reads that contain this k -mer. In this example, k -mer CAAT is present only in the blue-labelled sequence at the first position. Thus, both the initial end and start coordinates of the corresponding read are 13.

As the ends and starts of the reads are set, the graph is traversed forwards in batches (Figure 3.1iii) moving forwards using a breadth-first approach. The traversal halts upon reaching the maximum batch size.

At each batch traversal iteration, the annotations of the nodes in the batch are decompressed (Figure 3.2i) and collected into the separate structure to be used during the path tracing step. Note that in the considered case, the input node contains only the blue-labelled annotations, which means that the corresponding k -mer is present only in the blue-labelled read sequence.

Figure 3.1. The algorithm execution begins with the following steps: **i)** The graph constructed from sequences in Example 3.1. The query CAAT is mapped to the root node of the graph. **ii)** Before the traversal, the annotations for the input node are decompressed to set the coordinates of the input k -mer as the starts and ends of the reads. These start and end coordinates will be updated during the traversal. **iii)** During the traversal the nodes are collected in batches following the breadth-first strategy.

Figure 3.2. A single iteration of the traversal involves operating on the batch of nodes. **i)** Decompression of the annotations for the batch of visited nodes. **ii)** Update of the coordinates that mark ends of reads. By checking the increase of the coordinates consistent with the path in the graph, the largest coordinate is selected as the new read end. **iii)** For each of the updated read ends the successors are inspected for possible continuation. The found successors with increased coordinates are collected into a fresh empty queue which will be used for the traversal of the next batch.

The red coordinates are depicted for illustrative purposes and do not play a role in the read extraction process.

Further, the newly discovered coordinates are utilized to update the

known coordinates of the ends of reads (Figure 3.2ii). The updated reads' ends are checked for continuations in the adjacent outgoing nodes (Figure 3.2iii). The found successors with the increased coordinates serve as starting points for the traversal of the next batches. Accordingly, if none are found, the traversal stops.

Finally, the visited nodes and their annotations, which contain sample labels and k -mer coordinates, are used to trace the paths in the graphs which correspond to the read sequences. Since the starts and ends of the reads are known, they are exploited as separators for the collected k -mers that belong to the same sample.

Proposition 3.2. *Algorithm 2 finishes for every input row index.*

Proof. As the forward traversal is stopped when no continuations of reads are found in the successors, the algorithm stops traversal either in the sink nodes or in the nodes corresponding to the k -mers with the highest coordinates that can be reached by the path from the input node. Similarly, the backward traversal stops either in the source nodes or in the nodes that correspond to the k -mers with the smallest coordinates that can be reached by the path from the input node. Since the coordinates of a read are finite and strongly monotone, the termination of the traversal in both directions is guaranteed. \square

Proposition 3.3. *Algorithm 2 returns all paths that correspond to read sequences and include the input node.*

Proof. Since the coordinates of the input k -mer are initialized as read ends during the first step of the algorithm, Algorithm 2 traverses all paths that exhibit a consistent increase in coordinates starting from the input k -mer. As a result, no k -mers from the relevant read sequences are missed. \square

Algorithm 2 Trace Paths

Input: *row* (an index of the k -mer in the annotation matrix)

Output: *result* (a vector of tuples, each containing a vector of *row* indexes representing a path in the graph corresponding to a read, a label of the sample containing the read and the position of the input k -mer in the read)

```

1: function GETTRACESWITHROW(row)
2:   input_annotations  $\leftarrow$  GETROWTUPLES(row) ▷ MetaGraph API
3:   /* Set coordinates of the start node as read ends */
4:   ends_of_reads  $\leftarrow$  FINDEENDS(input_annotations, i)
5:   /* A map that stores the true ends of reads */
6:   final_ends_of_reads  $\leftarrow$  an empty map of columns to set of coordinates
7:   set traversed_nodes  $\leftarrow$  an empty set of pairs  $\langle$ coordinate, node $\rangle$ 
8:
9:   /* Begin forward BFS traversal of the graph */
10:  queue Q  $\leftarrow$  an empty FIFO queue
11:  ENQUEUE(Q, row)
12:  while true do
13:    vector batch_of_rows  $\leftarrow$  an empty vector
14:    while Q  $\neq$   $\emptyset$  do
15:      v = DEQUEUE(Q)
16:      if v is visited then continue
17:      end if
18:      batch_of_rows.PUSHBACK(v)
19:      ENQUEUEADJACENTOUTGOINGNODES(Q, v)
20:      if batch_of_rows.size()  $\geq$  MaxBatchSize then break
21:      end if
22:    end while
23:    /* Decompress annotations for the batch of rows */
24:    batch_annotations  $\leftarrow$  GETROWTUPLES(batch_of_rows) ▷ MetaGraph API
25:    /* Collect newly traversed nodes and their coordinates */
26:    UPDATETRAVERSED(batch_of_rows, batch_annotations, traversed_nodes)
27:    /* Update read ends based on traversed nodes */
28:    UPDATEENDS(ends_of_reads, traversed_nodes)
29:    /* Check if graph has to be traversed more */
30:    traverse_more  $\leftarrow$  CHECKIFTRAVERSEMOREFORWARD(ends_of_reads,
31:      final_ends_of_reads)
32:    if not traverse_more then break
33:    end if
  
```

```

34:  /* Similarly, traverse the graph backwards */
35:  starts_of_reads ← FINDSTARTS(input_annotatons, i)
36:  /* A map that store the true starts of reads */
37:  final_starts_of_reads ← an empty map of columns to set of coordinates
38:  queue Q ← an empty FIFO queue
39:  ENQUEUE(Q, row)
40:  while true do
41:      vector batch_of_rows ← an empty vector
42:      while Q ≠ ∅ do
43:          v = DEQUEUE(Q)
44:          if v is visited then continue
45:          end if
46:          batch_of_rows.PUSHBACK(v)
47:          ENQUEUEADJACENTINCOMINGNODES(Q, v)
48:          if batch_of_rows.size() ≥ MaxBatchSize then break
49:          end if
50:      end while
51:      /* Decompress annotations for the batch of rows */
52:      batch_annotatons ← GETROWTUPLES(batch_of_rows) ▷ MetaGraph API
53:      /* Collect newly traversed nodes and their coordinates */
54:      UPDATETRAVERSED(batch_of_rows, batch_annotatons, traversed_nodes)
55:      /* Update reads starts based on traversed nodes */
56:      UPDATESSTARTS(starts_of_reads, traversed_nodes)
57:      /* Check if graph has to be traversed backwards more */
58:      traverse_more ← CHECKIFTRAVERSEMOREBACKWARD(starts_of_reads,
59:          final_ends_of_reads)
60:      if not traverse_more then break
61:      end if
62:  end while
63:  /* Reconstruct the paths using coordinates */
64:  result ← TRACETHEPATHS(starts_of_reads,
65:      end_of_reads, traversed_nodes)
66:  return result
67: end function

```

Algorithm 3 Find Initial Ends of Reads

Input: *row_tuples* (vector of pairs $\langle \text{column}, \text{coordinates} \rangle$), *i* (index of the *k*-mer in the annotation matrix)

Output: *ends_of_reads* (map of *column* to set of *coordinates*)

```

1: function FINDENDS(row_tuples, i)
2:   map ends_of_reads  $\leftarrow$  map of column to set of k-mers' coordinates
3:   for (column, coordinates) in row_tuples do
4:     /* Start with the smallest coordinate */
5:     coord_1  $\leftarrow$  first coordinate in coordinates
6:     /* Find the increase in the adjacent outgoing nodes */
7:     for coord_2 in coordinates from the second element do
8:       edge_exists  $\leftarrow$  false
9:       for adj_outg_node in outgoing nodes of i do ▷ MetaGraph API
10:        if adj_outg_node equals i then
11:          edge_exists  $\leftarrow$  true
12:        end if
13:      end for
14:
15:      if (coord_2  $\neq$  (coord_1 + 1)) or not edge_exists then
16:        ends_of_reads[column].INSERT(coord_1)
17:      end if
18:      coord_1  $\leftarrow$  coord_2
19:    end for
20:    ends_of_reads[column].INSERT(coord_1)
21:  end for
22:  return ends_of_reads
23: end function

```

Algorithm 4 Enqueue Adjacent Outgoing Nodes

Input: *Q* (queue), *v* (index of the *k*-mer in the annotation matrix)

```

1: procedure ENQUEUEADJACENTOUTGOINGNODES(Q, v)
2:   for adj_outg_node in outgoing nodes if v do ▷ MetaGraph API
3:     ENQUEUE(Q, v)
4:   end for
5: end procedure

```

Algorithm 5 Update Ends of Reads

Input: *ends_of_reads* (map of *column* to set of *coordinates*), *traversed_nodes* (map of *column* to map of *coordinate* to *row* index)

```

1: procedure UPDATEENDS(ends_of_reads, traversed_nodes)
2:   for  $\langle \textit{column}, \textit{coordinates} \rangle$  in ends_of_reads do
3:     for end_coord in coordinates do
4:       end_row  $\leftarrow$  row index that corresponds to end_coord
5:       while traversed_nodes contains (read_end + 1) do
6:         candidate_end_row  $\leftarrow$  index that corresponds to (end_coord + 1)
7:
8:         for adj_outg_node in outgoing nodes of end_row do
9:           if adj_outg_node == candidate_end_row then
10:            /* Update current end with its continuation */
11:            ends_of_reads[column].ERASE(end_coord)
12:            ends_of_reads[column].INSERT((end_coord + 1))
13:          end if
14:        end for
15:
16:      end while
17:    end for
18:  end for
19: end procedure

```

Algorithm 6 Check If Graph Must Be Traversed More

Input: *ends_of_reads* (map of *column* to set of *coordinates*), *final_ends_of_reads* (map of *column* to set of *coordinates*), *traversed_nodes* (map of *column* to map of *coordinate* to *row* index)

Output: bool

```

1: function CHECKIFTRAVERSEMOREFORWARD(ends_of_reads,
   final_ends_of_reads, traversed_nodes)
2:   set successors  $\leftarrow$  an empty set of row indexes
3:   for  $\langle$ column,coordinates $\rangle$  in ends_of_reads do
4:     for end_coord in coordinates do
5:       end_row  $\leftarrow$  row index that corresponds to end_coord
6:       for adj_outg_node in outgoing nodes of end_row do  $\triangleright$  MetaGraph API
7:         successors.INSERT(adj_outg_node)
8:       end for
9:     end for
10:  end for
11:  /* Decompress annotations for the successors */
12:  successors_coordinates  $\leftarrow$  GETROWTUPLES(successors)
13:  queue Q_new  $\leftarrow$  an empty FIFO queue
14:  for  $\langle$ column,coordinates $\rangle$  in ends_of_reads do
15:    for end_coord in coordinates do
16:      /* Add the continuation to the queue */
17:      if successors_coordinates[column] contains (end_coord + 1) then
18:        successor_row  $\leftarrow$  row index that corresponds to (end_coord + 1)
19:        ENQUEUE(Q_new, successor_row)
20:      else
21:        /* If no continuation found then end_coord
22:        marks the true end of the read */
23:        ends_of_reads.ERASE(end_coord)
24:        final_ends_of_reads.INSERT(end_coord)
25:      end if
26:    end for
27:  end for
28:
29:  /* If the queue of continuations is empty, then the traversal is over */
30:  if Q_new.EMPTY() then
31:    return False
32:  else
33:    return True
34:  end if
35: end function

```

Chapter 4

Query experiments

4.1. Use case

To evaluate the proposed algorithm's feasibility, it was tested on *cDBGs* built from real-world samples containing SARS-CoV-2. The goal was to extract the reads that cover regions of the spike protein gene. The spike protein plays a vital role in the viral structure by serving as the primary target for the host's immune responses and therapeutic interventions. It is encoded by the spike protein gene, which is responsible for the protrusion of the spike protein from the viral envelope and facilitates its binding to specific receptors on the host cell surface. Therefore, the gene directly influences the infectivity and transmission of the virus. The SARS-CoV-2 virus has a total genome length of approximately 29.9 kilobases (kb) [21], with the spike protein gene situated between nucleotide positions 21,563 and 25,384 [28].

The reads which cover the spike protein gene can be used to assemble the full gene which would allow for the comparative analysis between different samples to explore the evolution of the virus. To extract these reads, we identified several regions of the spike protein gene that cover a wide range of the gene region span and tend to be stable across different variants. These regions are called conserved and served as the query sequences for the read extraction algorithm.

To determine the conserved regions, the Nextstrain [15] (<https://nextstrain.org/ncov/gisaid/global/6m>) resource was used. Based on the entropy chart, the segments of the spike protein gene with the entropy

value at the amino-acid level of no more than 0.007 were selected as the query sequences for the read extraction algorithm. Specifically, the query *fasta* file contained the following sequences:

```
>NC_045512.2:21660-21710
CACGTGGTGTATTATTACCCTGACAAAGTTTTTCAGATCCTCAGTTTTACATT
>NC_045512.2:22820-22870
GATTATAATTATAAATTACCAGATGATTTTTACAGGCTGCGTTATAGCTTGG
>NC_045512.2:24150-24200
CTTTGCTCACAGATGAAATGATTGCTCAATACACTTCTGCACTGTTAGCGG
>NC_045512.2:24550-24600
GATCACAGGCAGACTTCAAAGTTTGCAGACATATGTGACTCAACAATTAAT
```

The sequences were derived from the record NC_045512.2, which represents the complete genome of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and is accessible from the NCBI nucleotide database [3]. The numbers in the headers of the sequences in the query file (e.g., 21660-21710) indicate 0-based nucleotide positions of the segments within the virus's complete genome. With an average read length of approximately 1 kb, the reads containing selected conserved regions will span the entire range of the spike protein gene.

4.2. Small graphs

The proposed algorithm was initially tested on small graphs that could be constructed on a local machine and contained only a few samples. Several viral samples from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) at EMBL-EBI [1] were selected for the experiments, allowing for the construction of graphs with 8 GB of RAM available. Specifically, the following viral samples were chosen for this purpose: SRR15378266, SRR15157037, SRR9192558 (utilizing 20,000 first reads), SRR9719184 (utilizing 80,000 first reads), and SRR961669. Among these samples, only SRR15378266 and SRR15157037 contained the SARS-CoV-2 virus, while the remaining samples (SRR9192558, SRR9719184,

and SRR961669) comprised unrelated sequencing data from other viruses, such as Herpes virus or HIV. The raw sequencing data from these samples was used to construct *cDBGs* iteratively, gradually introducing irrelevant data. All the graphs were built with a value of $k = 31$. The resulting *cDBGs* are summarized in Table 4.1.

To evaluate the algorithm’s scalability, the constructed *cDBG* indexes were then used to run the algorithm with different batch size values, using the conserved regions of the spike protein gene described in Section 4.1 as the query. The purpose of this test was to observe how the performance of the read extraction algorithm changes when the graph is augmented with samples that do not contain reads overlapping with the given query.

Constructed Graphs			
Graph	Raw Size	<i>cDBG</i> Index Size	Stored Samples
<i>cDBG</i> 1	113 MB	15 MB	SRR15378266 , SRR15157037
<i>cDBG</i> 2	811 MB	251 MB	SRR15378266 , SRR15157037 , SRR9192558
<i>cDBG</i> 2	1.4 GB	334 MB	SRR15378266 , SRR15157037 , SRR9192558, SRR9719184, SRR961669

Table 4.1. Test graphs constructed from different samples. Samples containing SARS-CoV-2 are shown in bold.

During the algorithm execution, all the query sequences were processed in parallel which resulted in total execution time summarized in Table 4.2. Figure 4.1 provides a visualisation of the algorithm evaluation on the considered graphs specified in Table 4.2. The machine specifications are Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8265U CPU @ 1.60GHz, 8 GB of RAM + 10 GB of Swap.

One can see that for all considered batch size values, the execution time of the proposed algorithm does not increase at the same rate as the size of the constructed *cDBG* grows. Since the initial step of the algorithm involves

Read Extraction Algorithm Execution Time			
Graph	Batch Size 300	Batch Size 1000	Batch Size 5000
<i>cDBG 1</i>	30.5 sec	28.8 sec	33.5 sec
<i>cDBG 2</i>	33.6 sec	33.8 sec	37.7 sec
<i>cDBG 2</i>	35.2 sec	34.5 sec	37.8 sec

Table 4.2. The running time of the read extraction algorithm for each of the constructed graphs for different batch sizes. It can be noticed that the read extraction time does not significantly increase as the *cDBG* size grows.

Figure 4.1. The read extraction algorithm running time for the graphs specified in Table 4.1 performed with different batch size value.

mapping the k -mer to the node, the traversal immediately starts from the relevant part of the graph. Thus, the presence of samples which contain organisms other than the SARS-CoV-2 virus does not significantly affect the algorithm performance.

Furthermore, the traversal batch size of 1000 appeared to be the best value among those tested. Since the graph traversal and the annotation

decompression are two separate steps of the algorithm, the unnecessary nodes will be inevitably visited during the former. This depends on the internal structure of the underlying *DBG*. The balance between traversing too many of the irrelevant nodes and checking if the traversal must be continued is achieved by tuning the batch size parameter.

4.3. Huge graphs

The algorithm was also tested on a *cDBG* index that comprises 152,884 viral samples, with a total size of 171 GB. Specifically, the *cDBG* consisting of the graph of size 30 GB and the annotations of size 141 GB was provided by ETH Zurich for the experiments. The complete statistics of the graph can be found in Table 4.3.

Graph Stats				
Graph Size	k	Number of Nodes	Annotations Size	Number of Labels
30 GB	31	$1.11 \cdot 10^{11}$	141 GB	152884

Table 4.3. Stats of the *cDBG* index provided by ETH Zurich. Number of labels in the annotations matrix corresponds to the number of samples encompassed in the graph.

Since the *cDBG* comprises an extensive amount of samples, extracting the reads for all of them at once would not be feasible. Thus, in addition to the query sequences representing conserved regions of the spike protein gene (Section 4.1), the labels of the samples of interest for extracting the reads were specified before the algorithm started. Namely, the accession numbers of 10 samples containing the delta variant of SARS-CoV-2 were specified so that during the decompression steps only the relevant sample labels were considered (see Section 3.3). The mentioned sample identifiers are:

SRR15932294 SRR15787457 SRR15640855 SRR15938406 SRR15789592
 SRR15378266 SRR15934448 SRR15577801 SRR15157037 SRR15763843

Similarly to the experiments described in Section 4.2, all the query sequences were processed in parallel, and the extraction of reads was tested using different batch size values. The query experiments against the graph described in Table 4.3 were conducted on a remote machine provided by ETH Zurich. The machine specifications are Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz, 512 GB of RAM + 4 GB of Swap.

A summary of the experiments is shown in Table 4.4 which contains the average algorithm execution time for the 4 conserved regions introduced in Section 4.1. The columns represent the average time spent on forward and backward local traversal of the graph, decompression of the annotations for the batches of nodes, and determining whether there are continuations beyond the ends and starts of reads that require further graph traversal. The complete information on query experiments for each of the considered query sequences can be found in Appendix 1.1.

Average Read Extraction Algorithm Execution Time					
Batch Size	Forward Trav.	Backward Trav.	Decompression	Check	Total
1000	43 sec	229 sec	25.2 hrs	21 hrs	47 hrs
8000	120 sec	766 sec	23.6 hrs	12 hrs	36.6 hrs
15000	236 sec	1085 sec	25.1 hrs	10.7 hrs	36.9 hrs

Table 4.4. The average running time of the read extraction algorithm for the query sequences described in Section 4.1 for the *cDBG* provided by ETH Zurich which contains viral sequencing data. The stats of the graph are indicated in Table 4.3.

From the results of query experiments for different batch size values indicated in Table 4.4, it can be noticed that decompressing the nodes' annotations and exploring the ends and starts of the reads for possible continuations are the most time-consuming steps of the algorithm. In contrast, since the local graph traversal is done on the BOSS table, this step takes less than 1% of the total execution time. Moreover, with the increase of the batch size, the time spent on local traversal and decompression of the annotations

increases. At the same time, the time spent on performing checks on whether further traversal is needed decreases as the larger batch size results in bigger traversal steps with fewer checks.

Based on the data presented in Table 4.4, it was observed that the average read extraction time was minimized when employing a batch size of 8000, out of the tested values. However, further optimization of this parameter may potentially yield better results.

Figure 4.2. A phylogenetic cladogram of the assembled and aligned spike protein gene sequences for 10 samples containing the delta variant of SARS-CoV-2. The phylogenetic tree is calculated based on the distance matrix of the aligned sequences. The numbers indicate the distance to the first common ancestor. The exact order of the branches is irrelevant. It can be observed that samples SRR15157037, SRR15934448 and SRR15378266 have the smallest absolute distance values which indicates their similarity.

Figure 4.3. A visualization of the multiple sequence alignment result obtained using MView [9]. The region of the spike protein gene spanning from the nucleotide position 3041 to position 3120 is displayed. In such representation, the similarities and differences between multiple organisms can be explored visually. For example, for samples SRR15934448 and SRR15378266, the 99.7% and 99.5% of nucleotides respectively matched with the sample SRR15157037. This echoes the clustering result obtained in Figure 4.2.

The extracted reads were used to assemble the spike protein gene for each of the samples separately. The reads in the considered samples are mai-

nly obtained with the PacBio HIFI Sequencing technology. Thus, for the assembly step, the *hifiasm* [11] assembler was used as it operates on the long sequence reads. The obtained assemblies were then aligned with the help of the *mafft* [20] multiple sequence aligner. Finally, the alignment result was visualized using the MView tool [9].

Such a pipeline describes a possible use case when a large-scale comparative analysis of various organisms is needed to be performed. After the extraction, reads can be used for biological inference (Figures 4.2, 4.3) of possible evolutionary, functional or structural relationships across different organisms or strains.

Results

The developed read extraction algorithm enables the reconstruction of original read sequences from a *Counting de Bruijn graph*. Local experiments, as described in Section 4.2, indicate that the read reconstruction time remains relatively unchanged when new irrelevant samples are added to the graph index. Since the graph is constructed based on k -mers, each organism's specific k -mers are implicitly represented as a subgraph. The distinctiveness of the k -mers results in more separated parts of the graph. Consequently, as the algorithm immediately starts the traversal from the nodes corresponding to the query sequence, only the neighbouring k -mers significantly impact the performance. Furthermore, by adjusting the batch size parameter, the traversal step can be optimized. The optimal value for this parameter depends on the structure of the graph and its annotations. Typically, the batch size should be large enough to efficiently decompress the batch annotations while minimizing the need for additional graph traversal. However, an excessively large batch size may lead to visiting irrelevant nodes since the traversal is performed on the graph itself without considering annotations to guide the traversal.

On the other hand, query experiments conducted on a graph index encompassing hundreds of thousands of samples (Section 4.3) resulted in extraction times of more than 35 hours to retrieve reads for a subset of 10 samples. The significant number of matching reads stored in the graph contributes to the time-consuming selection process even if only a small portion of relevant reads needs to be extracted.

The implemented algorithm is available as a query option, `--query-reads`, in the fork of the *MetaGraph* framework. The forked version can be accessed at <https://github.com/d-goryslavets/metagraph>.

Conclusions

This work has presented a read extraction algorithm from *Counting de Bruijn graphs*, offering a valuable tool for selecting sequences of interest from the constructed graph index. This approach provides an alternative to searching raw sequences in public databases, allowing for efficient storage and retrieval of sequencing data.

Moving forward, there are several avenues for future research and improvement. One area of focus could be the fine-tuning of batch sizes for different types of graphs. By optimizing the batch size parameter, the algorithm's performance can be further enhanced, taking into account the specific characteristics and structures of various graph representations.

Additionally, the most time-consuming steps of the algorithm which are the decompression of the annotations and checking if further traversal is required have a lot of room for optimization. Potential improvements in these steps may result in a more efficient algorithm.

Overall, this work establishes the read extraction algorithm as a valuable addition to the existing repertoire of query methods for *Counting de Bruijn graphs*. By enabling retrieval of relevant reads from the graph index, the algorithm enhances the utility of these graphs in genomics research and lays the groundwork for further enhancements of the read extraction query.

References

1. European Nucleotide Archive at EMBL-EBI [Internet] - [cited 2023 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/>.
2. MetaGraph [Internet] - [cited 2023 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://metagraph.ethz.ch/>.
3. Nucleotide [Internet]. Bethesda (md): National Library of Medicine (US), National Center for Biotechnology Information; 2004 – [cited 2023 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/>.
4. Fatemeh Almodaresi, Prashant Pandey, and Rob Patro. Rainbowfish: A succinct colored de bruijn graph representation. May 2017.
5. Fatemeh Almodaresi, Mohsen Zakeri, and Rob Patro. PuffAligner: a fast, efficient and accurate aligner based on the Pufferfish index. *Bioinformatics*, 37(22):4048–4055, 06 2021.
6. Gaëtan Benoit, Mahendra Mariadassou, Stéphane Robin, Sophie Schbath, Pierre Peterlongo, and Claire Lemaitre. SimkaMin: fast and resource frugal de novo comparative metagenomics. *Bioinformatics*, 36(4):1275–1276, September 2019.
7. Alexander Bowe. Succinct de Bruijn graphs [Internet] - [cited 2023 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://www.alexbowe.com/succinct-debruijn-graphs/>.
8. Alexander Bowe, Taku Onodera, Kunihiko Sadakane, and Tetsuo Shibuya. Succinct de bruijn graphs. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 225–235. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012.

9. N P Brown, C Leroy, and C Sander. MView: a web-compatible database search or multiple alignment viewer. *Bioinformatics*, 14(4):380–381, January 1998.
10. N.G. Bruijn, de. A combinatorial problem. *Proceedings of the Section of Sciences of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen te Amsterdam*, 49(7):758–764, 1946.
11. Haoyu Cheng, Gregory T. Concepcion, Xiaowen Feng, Haowen Zhang, and Heng Li. Haplotype-resolved de novo assembly using phased assembly graphs with hifiasm. *Nature Methods*, 18(2):170–175, February 2021.
12. Illyoung Choi, Alise J Ponsero, Matthew Bomhoff, Ken Youens-Clark, John H Hartman, and Bonnie L Hurwitz. Libra: scalable k-mer-based tool for massive all-vs-all metagenome comparisons. *GigaScience*, 8(2), December 2018.
13. Daniel Danciu, Mikhail Karasikov, Harun Mustafa, André Kahles, and Gunnar Rätsch. Topology-based sparsification of graph annotations. *Bioinformatics*, 37(Supplement_1):i169–i176, July 2021.
14. David Danko et al. A global metagenomic map of urban microbiomes and antimicrobial resistance. *Cell*, 184(13):3376–3393.e17, 2021.
15. James Hadfield, Colin Megill, Sidney M Bell, John Huddleston, Barney Potter, Charlton Callender, Pavel Sagulenko, Trevor Bedford, and Richard A Neher. Nextstrain: real-time tracking of pathogen evolution. *Bioinformatics*, 34(23):4121–4123, 05 2018.
16. Zamin Iqbal, Mario Caccamo, Isaac Turner, Paul Fliccek, and Gil McVean. De novo assembly and genotyping of variants using colored de bruijn graphs. *Nature Genetics*, 44(2):226–232, January 2012.

17. Mikhail Karasikov, Harun Mustafa, Daniel Danciu, Marc Zimmermann, Christopher Barber, Gunnar Rätsch, and André Kahles. Metagraph: Indexing and analysing nucleotide archives at petabase-scale. *bioRxiv*, 2020.
18. Mikhail Karasikov, Harun Mustafa, Amir Joudaki, Sara Javadzadeh-No, Gunnar Rätsch, and André Kahles. Sparse binary relation representations for genome graph annotation. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 120–135. Springer International Publishing, 2019.
19. Mikhail Karasikov, Harun Mustafa, Gunnar Rätsch, and André Kahles. Lossless indexing with counting de bruijn graphs. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 374–376. Springer International Publishing, 2022.
20. Kazutaka Katoh, Kazuharu Misawa, Kei-ichi Kuma, and Takashi Miyata. MAFFT: a novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 30(14):3059–3066, 07 2002.
21. Rozhgar A. Khailany, Muhamad Safdar, and Mehmet Ozaslan. Genomic characterization of a novel SARS-CoV-2. *Gene Reports*, 19:100682, June 2020.
22. Bo Liu, Hongzhe Guo, Michael Brudno, and Yadong Wang. deBGA: read alignment with de Bruijn graph-based seed and extension. *Bioinformatics*, 32(21):3224–3232, 07 2016.
23. Nina Luhmann, Guillaume Holley, and Mark Achtman. BlastFrost: fast querying of 100, 000s of bacterial genomes in bifrost graphs. *Genome Biology*, 22(1), January 2021.
24. Brian D. Ondov, Todd J. Treangen, Páll Melsted, Adam B. Mallonee, Nicholas H. Bergman, Sergey Koren, and Adam M. Phillippy. Mash: fast

- genome and metagenome distance estimation using MinHash. *Genome Biology*, 17(1), June 2016.
25. Prashant Pandey, Fatemeh Almodaresi, Michael A. Bender, Michael Ferdman, Rob Johnson, and Rob Patro. Mantis: A fast, small, and exact large-scale sequence-search index. *Cell Systems*, 7(2):201–207.e4, 2018.
 26. Zachary D. Stephens, Skylar Y. Lee, Faraz Faghri, Roy H. Campbell, Chengxiang Zhai, Miles J. Efron, Ravishankar Iyer, Michael C. Schatz, Saurabh Sinha, and Gene E. Robinson. Big data: Astronomical or genomics? *PLOS Biology*, 13(7):1–11, 07 2015.
 27. Karl V Voelkerding, Shale A Dames, and Jacob D Durtschi. Next-generation sequencing: From basic research to diagnostics. *Clinical Chemistry*, 55(4):641–658, April 2009.
 28. Francis K. Yoshimoto. The proteins of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS CoV-2 or n-COV19), the cause of COVID-19. *The Protein Journal*, 39(3):198–216, May 2020.

Appendix 1

Query experiments

1.1. Huge graphs

Tables 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 summarize the results of the query experiments described in Section 4.3 for each query sequence separately.

Read Extraction Execution Time For Query NC_045512.2:21660-21710					
Batch Size	Forward Trav.	Backward Trav.	Decompression	Check	Total
1000	45 sec	177 sec	27.3 hrs	23.2 hrs	51.3 hrs
8000	130 sec	615 sec	26.3 hrs	14.9 hrs	42.2 hrs
15000	239 sec	812 sec	26.7 hrs	12.6 hrs	40.3 hrs

Table 1.1. The read extraction algorithm execution time from the *cDBG* described in Table 4.3 using the conserved region of the spike protein with header NC_045512.2:21660-21710 as a query sequence.

Read Extraction Execution Time For Query NC_045512.2:22820-22870					
Batch Size	Forward Trav.	Backward Trav.	Decompression	Check	Total
1000	28 sec	248 sec	23.8 hrs	21.5 hrs	46.3 hrs
8000	81 sec	828 sec	20.7 hrs	11.6 hrs	33.6 hrs
15000	155 sec	1165 sec	20.8 hrs	9.6 hrs	31.7 hrs

Table 1.2. The read extraction algorithm execution time from the *cDBG* described in Table 4.3 using the conserved region of the spike protein with header NC_045512.2:22820-22870 as a query sequence.

Read Extraction Execution Time For Query NC_045512.2:24150-24200					
Batch Size	Forward Trav.	Backward Trav.	Decompression	Check	Total
1000	50 sec	247 sec	24.8 hrs	19.5 hrs	44.9 hrs
8000	132 sec	820 sec	23.8 hrs	10.9 hrs	35.4 hrs
15000	276 sec	1189 sec	26.9 hrs	10.7 hrs	38.4 hrs

Table 1.3. The read extraction algorithm execution time from the *cDBG* described in Table 4.3 using the conserved region of the spike protein with header NC_045512.2:24150-24200 as a query sequence.

Read Extraction Execution Time For Query NC_045512.2:24550-24600					
Batch Size	Forward Trav.	Backward Trav.	Decompression	Check	Total
1000	50 sec	247 sec	25.0 hrs	19.9 hrs	45.6 hrs
8000	136 sec	800 sec	23.7 hrs	10.9 hrs	35.4 hrs
15000	274 sec	1173 sec	26.3 hrs	10.1 hrs	37.4 hrs

Table 1.4. The read extraction algorithm execution time from the *cDBG* described in Table 4.3 using the conserved region of the spike protein with header NC_045512.2:24550-24600 as a query sequence.

Appendix 2

Algorithm implementation

2.1. Path tracing method

The method returns paths in a graph which contain the input node passed as the index of the row in the annotations matrix. The implementation is done within the `TupleRowDiff` class which extends the `IRowDiff` and `MultiIntMatrix` classes and describes the interface for operating on the annotations matrix that stores k -mer coordinates and is compressed using the *RowDiff* technique.

```
template <class BaseMatrix>
std::vector<std::tuple<std::vector<MultiIntMatrix::Row>, MultiIntMatrix::
    Column, uint64_t>> TupleRowDiff<BaseMatrix>
::get_traces_with_row(Row i, std::unordered_set<uint64_t>
    labels_of_interest, std::unordered_map<Column, std::vector<std::tuple<
    std::vector<Row>, uint64_t, uint64_t>>> &reconstructed_reads) const {
    std::vector<std::tuple<std::vector<Row>, Column, uint64_t>> result;
    std::unordered_map<Column, std::unordered_set<uint64_t>>
        start_coords_of_already_reconstructed_reads;
    std::unordered_map<Column, std::map<uint64_t, Row>> reconstructed_paths;
    RowTuples input_row_tuples = get_row_tuples(i);
    for (auto &[j, tuple] : input_row_tuples) {
        if (!labels_of_interest.count(j))
            continue;
        for (uint64_t &c : tuple) {
            bool already_in_the_read = false;
            for (auto &[already_reconstructed_read, first_coord_of_read,
                last_coord_of_read] : reconstructed_reads[j]) {
                if ((c >= first_coord_of_read && c <= last_coord_of_read)) {
                    already_in_the_read = true;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

        result.push_back(std::make_tuple(already_reconstructed_read, j, c
            - first_coord_of_read));
        start_coords_of_already_reconstructed_reads[j].insert(
            first_coord_of_read);
        break;
    }
}
if (already_in_the_read)
    continue;
reconstructed_paths[j][c] = i;
}
}
input_row_tuples = RowTuples();
if (reconstructed_paths.empty())
    return result;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>> ends_of_reads;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>> starts_of_reads;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>> ends_of_reads_final;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>> starts_of_reads_final;
for (auto &[j, coords] : reconstructed_paths) {
    auto node_1 = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(
        coords.begin()->second);
    auto coord_1 = coords.begin()->first;
    for (auto iter_map = std::next(coords.begin()); iter_map != coords.end()
        (); ++iter_map) {
        auto node_2 = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(
            iter_map->second);
        auto coord_2 = iter_map->first;
        bool edge_exists = false;
        graph->adjacent_outgoing_nodes(node_1, [&](auto adj_outg_node) {
            if (adj_outg_node == node_2) {
                edge_exists = true;
                return;
            }
        });
        if (!(coord_2 == (coord_1 + SHIFT)) && edge_exists)
            ends_of_reads[j].insert(coord_1);
        node_1 = node_2;
        coord_1 = coord_2;
    }
    ends_of_reads[j].insert(coord_1);
    auto node_1_start = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(
        coords.rbegin()->second);
    auto coord_1_start = coords.rbegin()->first;

```

```

for (auto iter_map = std::next(coords.rbegin()); iter_map != coords.
    rend(); ++iter_map) {
    auto node_2 = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(
        iter_map->second);
    auto coord_2 = iter_map->first;
    bool edge_exists = false;
    graph->adjacent_incoming_nodes(node_1_start, [&](auto adj_inc_node)
        {
            if (adj_inc_node == node_2) {
                edge_exists = true;
                return;
            }
        });
    if (!(coord_2 == (coord_1_start - SHIFT)) && edge_exists)
        starts_of_reads[j].insert(coord_1_start);
    node_1_start = node_2;
    coord_1_start = coord_2;
}
starts_of_reads[j].insert(coord_1_start);
}
std::queue<Row> to_visit;
to_visit.push(i);
std::unordered_set<Row> visited_nodes_forward;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>> all_discovered_coordinates
    ;
while (true) {
    uint64_t traversed_nodes_count = 0;
    std::vector<Row> batch_of_rows;
    while (!to_visit.empty()) {
        Row current_parent = to_visit.front();
        to_visit.pop();
        if (visited_nodes_forward.count(current_parent)) continue;
        batch_of_rows.push_back(current_parent);
        traversed_nodes_count++;
        graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::node_index current_parent_to_graph =
            graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(current_parent)
                ;
        graph->call_outgoing_kmers(current_parent_to_graph, [&](auto next,
            char c) {
            if (c == graph::boss::BOSS::kSentinel) return;
            Row next_to_anno = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
                graph_to_anno_index(next);
            to_visit.push(next_to_anno);
        });
        visited_nodes_forward.insert(current_parent);
    }
}

```

```

    if (traversed_nodes_count >= TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE) break;
}
std::vector<RowTuples> batch_annotations = get_row_tuples_labeled(
    batch_of_rows, labels_of_interest);
for (size_t batch_i = 0; batch_i < batch_of_rows.size(); ++batch_i) {
    for (auto &[j_next, tuple_next] : batch_annotations[batch_i]) {
        if (!labels_of_interest.count(j_next)) {
            tuple_next = Tuple();
            continue;
        }
        for (uint64_t &c_next : tuple_next) {
            all_discovered_coordinates[j_next].insert(c_next);
            reconstructed_paths[j_next][c_next] = batch_of_rows[batch_i];
        }
        tuple_next = Tuple();
    }
}
batch_annotations = std::vector<RowTuples>();
batch_of_rows = std::vector<Row>();
std::unordered_map<Column, std::vector<std::pair<uint64_t, uint64_t>>>
    ends_to_update;
for (auto &[j_end, coords_ends] : ends_of_reads) {
    for (auto &c_end : coords_ends) {
        auto c_end_curr = c_end;
        bool replace_read_end = false;
        auto end_node_old = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
            anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_end][c_end_curr]);
        while (all_discovered_coordinates[j_end].count(c_end_curr + SHIFT))
            {
                auto end_node_new = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
                    anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_end][c_end_curr +
                    SHIFT]);
                bool edge_exists = false;
                graph->adjacent_outgoing_nodes(end_node_old, [&](auto
                    adj_outg_node) {
                    if (adj_outg_node == end_node_new) {
                        edge_exists = true;
                        return;
                    }
                });
                if (edge_exists) {
                    end_node_old = end_node_new;
                    replace_read_end = true;
                    c_end_curr += SHIFT;
                } else {

```

```

        break;
    }
}
if (replace_read_end)
    ends_to_update[j_end].push_back(std::make_pair(c_end, c_end_curr)
    );
}
}
for (auto &[j_to_update, old_new_ends_to_update] : ends_to_update) {
    for (auto &[c_end_old, c_end_updated] : old_new_ends_to_update) {
        ends_of_reads[j_to_update].erase(c_end_old);
        ends_of_reads[j_to_update].insert(c_end_updated);
    }
}
to_visit = std::deque<Row>();
std::unordered_set<Row> batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set;
for (auto &[j_end, coords_ends] : ends_of_reads) {
    for (auto &c_end : coords_ends) {
        auto end_node_old = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
            anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_end][c_end]);
        graph->call_outgoing_kmers(end_node_old, [&](auto adj_outg_node,
            char c) {
            if (c == graph::boss::BOSS::kSentinel) return;
            Row adj_outg_to_anno = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
                graph_to_anno_index(adj_outg_node);
            batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.insert(
                adj_outg_to_anno);
        });
    }
}
std::vector<Row> batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more;
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.reserve(
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.size());
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.insert(
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.end(),
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.begin(),
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.end());
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set = std::unordered_set<Row>()
;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::unordered_set<uint64_t>>
    coordinates_of_the_successors;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::unordered_map<uint64_t, Row>>
    successors_rows_and_coords;
size_t batch_vec_size = batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.size();

```

```

for (size_t cur_part = 0; cur_part < batch_vec_size; cur_part +=
    TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE) {
    size_t cur_end = std::min(cur_part + TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE,
        batch_vec_size);
    std::vector<Row> batch_part(batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.
        begin() + cur_part,
        batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.begin() + cur_end);
    std::vector<RowTuples> batch_part_annotations =
        get_row_tuples_labeled(batch_part, labels_of_interest);
    for (size_t rowt_to_check = 0; rowt_to_check < batch_part.size(); ++
        rowt_to_check) {
        for (auto &[j_to_check, tuple_to_check] : batch_part_annotations[
            rowt_to_check]) {
            if (!labels_of_interest.count(j_to_check)) {
                tuple_to_check = Tuple();
                continue;
            }
            for (auto &c_to_check : tuple_to_check) {
                coordinates_of_the_successors[j_to_check].insert(c_to_check);
                successors_rows_and_coords[j_to_check][c_to_check] = batch_part
                    [rowt_to_check];
            }
            tuple_to_check = Tuple();
        }
    }
    batch_part_annotations = std::vector<RowTuples>();
}
for (auto &[j_end, coords_ends] : ends_of_reads) {
    for (auto it_end_coords = coords_ends.begin(); it_end_coords !=
        coords_ends.end(); ) {
        if (coordinates_of_the_successors[j_end].count(*it_end_coords +
            SHIFT)) {
            to_visit.push(successors_rows_and_coords[j_end][*it_end_coords +
                SHIFT]);
            visited_nodes_forward.erase(successors_rows_and_coords[j_end][*
                it_end_coords + SHIFT]);
            ++it_end_coords;
        } else {
            ends_of_reads_final[j_end].insert(*it_end_coords);
            it_end_coords = coords_ends.erase(it_end_coords);
        }
    }
}
std::vector<Column> labels_to_clean_up;

```

```

for (auto &j_clean_up, coords_and_rows_clean_up] : reconstructed_paths
    ) {
    if ((ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty() && ends_of_reads_final[
        j_clean_up].empty()) || starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        labels_to_clean_up.push_back(j_clean_up);
        continue;
    }
    uint64_t max_end_of_read;
    uint64_t min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].begin());
    if (ends_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].rbegin());
    } else if (ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].rbegin());
    } else {
        max_end_of_read = std::max(*(ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].rbegin()),
            *(ends_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].rbegin()));
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.rbegin();
        it_clean_up != coords_and_rows_clean_up.rend(); ) {
        if (it_clean_up->first > max_end_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = decltype(it_clean_up)(coords_and_rows_clean_up.
                erase(std::next(it_clean_up).base()));
        } else {
            break;
        }
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.begin(); it_clean_up
        != coords_and_rows_clean_up.end(); ) {
        if (it_clean_up->first < min_start_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.erase(it_clean_up);
        } else {
            break;
        }
    }
}
for (auto &j_clean_up : labels_to_clean_up)
    reconstructed_paths.erase(j_clean_up);
labels_to_clean_up = std::vector<Column>();
for (auto &j_to_clean_discovered_coords, discovered_coords] :
    all_discovered_coordinates) {
    if ((ends_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty() &&
        ends_of_reads_final[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) ||
        starts_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) {
        labels_to_clean_up.push_back(j_to_clean_discovered_coords);
    }
}

```

```

        continue;
    }
    uint64_t max_end_of_read;
    uint64_t min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads[
        j_to_clean_discovered_coords].begin());
    if (ends_of_reads_final[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) {
        max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].
            rbegin());
    } else if (ends_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) {
        max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads_final[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].rbegin());
    } else {
        max_end_of_read = std::max(*(ends_of_reads[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].rbegin()), *(ends_of_reads_final[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].rbegin()));
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = discovered_coords.rbegin(); it_clean_up !=
        discovered_coords.rend(); ) {
        if (*it_clean_up > max_end_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = decltype(it_clean_up)(discovered_coords.erase(std::
                next(it_clean_up).base()));
        } else {
            break;
        }
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = discovered_coords.begin(); it_clean_up !=
        discovered_coords.end(); ) {
        if (*it_clean_up < min_start_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = discovered_coords.erase(it_clean_up);
        } else {
            break;
        }
    }
    for (auto &j_clean_up : labels_to_clean_up)
        all_discovered_coordinates.erase(j_clean_up);
    if (to_visit.empty())
        break;
}
ends_of_reads = ends_of_reads_final;
ends_of_reads_final = std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>>();
to_visit = std::queue<Row>();
to_visit.push(i);
std::unordered_set<Row> visited_nodes_backward;
while (true) {

```

```

uint64_t traversed_nodes_count = 0;
std::vector<Row> batch_of_rows;
while (!to_visit.empty()) {
    Row current_child = to_visit.front();
    to_visit.pop();
    if (visited_nodes_backward.count(current_child)) continue;
    batch_of_rows.push_back(current_child);
    traversed_nodes_count++;
    graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::node_index current_child_to_graph =
        graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::anno_to_graph_index(current_child);
    graph->call_incoming_kmers(current_child_to_graph, [&](auto prev,
        char c) {
        if (c == graph::boss::BOSS::kSentinel) return;
        Row prev_to_anno = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
            graph_to_anno_index(prev);
        to_visit.push(prev_to_anno);
    });
    visited_nodes_backward.insert(current_child);
    if (traversed_nodes_count >= TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE) break;
}
std::vector<RowTuples> batch_annotations = get_row_tuples_labeled(
    batch_of_rows, labels_of_interest);
for (size_t batch_i = 0; batch_i < batch_of_rows.size(); ++batch_i) {
    for (auto &[j_prev, tuple_prev] : batch_annotations[batch_i]) {
        if (!labels_of_interest.count(j_prev)) {
            tuple_prev = Tuple();
            continue;
        }
        for (uint64_t &c_prev : tuple_prev) {
            all_discovered_coordinates[j_prev].insert(c_prev);
            reconstructed_paths[j_prev][c_prev] = batch_of_rows[batch_i];
        }
        tuple_prev = Tuple();
    }
}
batch_annotations = std::vector<RowTuples>();
batch_of_rows = std::vector<Row>();
std::unordered_map<Column, std::vector<std::pair<uint64_t, uint64_t>>>
    starts_to_update;
for (auto &[j_start, coords_starts] : starts_of_reads) {
    for (auto &c_start : coords_starts) {
        if (c_start == 0)
            continue;
        auto c_start_curr = c_start;
        bool replace_read_start = false;

```

```

auto start_node_old = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
    anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_start][c_start_curr]);
while (all_discovered_coordinates[j_start].count(c_start_curr -
    SHIFT)) {
    auto start_node_new = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
        anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_start][c_start_curr
        - SHIFT]);
    bool edge_exists = false;
    graph->adjacent_incoming_nodes(start_node_old, [&](auto
        adj_inc_node) {
        if (adj_inc_node == start_node_new) {
            edge_exists = true;
            return;
        }
    });
    if (edge_exists) {
        start_node_old = start_node_new;
        replace_read_start = true;
        c_start_curr -= SHIFT;
    } else {
        break;
    }
}
if (replace_read_start)
    starts_to_update[j_start].push_back(std::make_pair(c_start,
        c_start_curr));
}
}
for (auto &[j_to_update, old_new_starts_to_update] : starts_to_update)
{
    for (auto &[c_start_old, c_start_updated] : old_new_starts_to_update)
    {
        starts_of_reads[j_to_update].erase(c_start_old);
        starts_of_reads[j_to_update].insert(c_start_updated);
    }
}
to_visit = std::deque<Row>();
std::unordered_set<Row> batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set;
for (auto &[j_start, coords_starts] : starts_of_reads) {
    for (auto &c_start : coords_starts) {
        auto start_node_old = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
            anno_to_graph_index(reconstructed_paths[j_start][c_start]);
        graph->call_incoming_kmers(start_node_old, [&](auto adj_outg_node,
            char c) {
            if (c == graph::boss::BOSS::kSentinel) return;

```

```

        Row adj_inc_to_anno = graph::AnnotatedSequenceGraph::
            graph_to_anno_index(adj_outg_node);
        batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.insert(
            adj_inc_to_anno);
    });
}
}
std::vector<Row> batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more;
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.reserve(
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.size());
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.insert(
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.end(),
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.begin(),
    batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set.end());
batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more_set = std::unordered_set<Row>()
;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::unordered_set<uint64_t>>
    coordinates_of_the_predecessors;
std::unordered_map<Column, std::unordered_map<uint64_t, Row>>
    predecessors_rows_and_coords;
size_t batch_vec_size = batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.size();
for (size_t cur_part = 0; cur_part < batch_vec_size; cur_part +=
    TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE) {
    size_t cur_end = std::min(cur_part + TRAVERSAL_BATCH_SIZE,
        batch_vec_size);
    std::vector<Row> batch_part(batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.
        begin() + cur_part,
        batch_of_rows_to_check_if_traverse_more.begin() + cur_end);
    std::vector<RowTuples> batch_part_annotations =
        get_row_tuples_labeled(batch_part, labels_of_interest);
    for (size_t rowt_to_check = 0; rowt_to_check < batch_part.size(); ++
        rowt_to_check) {
        for (auto &[j_to_check, tuple_to_check] : batch_part_annotations[
            rowt_to_check]) {
            if (!labels_of_interest.count(j_to_check)) {
                tuple_to_check = Tuple();
                continue;
            }
            for (auto &c_to_check : tuple_to_check) {
                coordinates_of_the_predecessors[j_to_check].insert(c_to_check);
                predecessors_rows_and_coords[j_to_check][c_to_check] =
                    batch_part[rowt_to_check];
            }
            tuple_to_check = Tuple();
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
    batch_part_annotations = std::vector<RowTuples>();
}
for (auto &[j_start, coords_starts] : starts_of_reads) {
    for (auto it_start_coords = coords_starts.begin(); it_start_coords !=
        coords_starts.end(); ) {
        if (*it_start_coords == 0) {
            starts_of_reads_final[j_start].insert(*it_start_coords);
            it_start_coords = coords_starts.erase(it_start_coords);
        } else if (coordinates_of_the_predecessors[j_start].count(*
            it_start_coords - SHIFT)) {
            to_visit.push(predecessors_rows_and_coords[j_start][*
                it_start_coords - SHIFT]);
            visited_nodes_backward.erase(predecessors_rows_and_coords[j_start
                ][*it_start_coords - SHIFT]);
            ++it_start_coords;
        } else {
            starts_of_reads_final[j_start].insert(*it_start_coords);
            it_start_coords = coords_starts.erase(it_start_coords);
        }
    }
}
std::vector<Column> labels_to_clean_up;
for (auto &[j_clean_up, coords_and_rows_clean_up] : reconstructed_paths
    ) {
    if ((starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty() && starts_of_reads_final[
        j_clean_up].empty()) || ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        labels_to_clean_up.push_back(j_clean_up);
        continue;
    }
    uint64_t min_start_of_read;
    uint64_t max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads[j_clean_up].rbegin());
    if (starts_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].begin());
    } else if (starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].empty()) {
        min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].begin());
    } else {
        min_start_of_read = std::min(*(starts_of_reads[j_clean_up].begin())
            , *(starts_of_reads_final[j_clean_up].begin()));
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.rbegin();
        it_clean_up != coords_and_rows_clean_up.rend(); ) {
        if (it_clean_up->first > max_end_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = decltype(it_clean_up)(coords_and_rows_clean_up.
                erase(std::next(it_clean_up).base()));
        }
    }
}

```

```

    } else {
        break;
    }
}
for (auto it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.begin(); it_clean_up
    != coords_and_rows_clean_up.end(); ) {
    if (it_clean_up->first < min_start_of_read) {
        it_clean_up = coords_and_rows_clean_up.erase(it_clean_up);
    } else {
        break;
    }
}
}
for (auto &j_clean_up : labels_to_clean_up)
    reconstructed_paths.erase(j_clean_up);
labels_to_clean_up = std::vector<Column>();
for (auto &[j_to_clean_discovered_coords, discovered_coords] :
    all_discovered_coordinates) {
    if (ends_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty() || (
        starts_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty() &&
        starts_of_reads_final[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty())) {
        labels_to_clean_up.push_back(j_to_clean_discovered_coords);
        continue;
    }
    uint64_t min_start_of_read;
    uint64_t max_end_of_read = *(ends_of_reads[
        j_to_clean_discovered_coords].rbegin());
    if (starts_of_reads_final[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) {
        min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords
            ].begin());
    } else if (starts_of_reads[j_to_clean_discovered_coords].empty()) {
        min_start_of_read = *(starts_of_reads_final[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].begin());
    } else {
        min_start_of_read = std::min(*(starts_of_reads[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].begin()), *(starts_of_reads_final[
            j_to_clean_discovered_coords].begin()));
    }
    for (auto it_clean_up = discovered_coords.rbegin(); it_clean_up !=
        discovered_coords.rend(); ) {
        if (*it_clean_up > max_end_of_read) {
            it_clean_up = decltype(it_clean_up)(discovered_coords.erase(std::
                next(it_clean_up).base()));
        } else {
            break;
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
  }
  for (auto it_clean_up = discovered_coords.begin(); it_clean_up !=
       discovered_coords.end(); ) {
    if (*it_clean_up < min_start_of_read) {
      it_clean_up = discovered_coords.erase(it_clean_up);
    } else {
      break;
    }
  }
}
for (auto &j_clean_up : labels_to_clean_up)
  all_discovered_coordinates.erase(j_clean_up);
if (to_visit.empty())
  break;
}
starts_of_reads = starts_of_reads_final;
starts_of_reads_final = std::unordered_map<Column, std::set<uint64_t>>();
for (auto &[j_st, coords_st] : starts_of_reads) {
  auto it_start = coords_st.begin();
  auto it_end = ends_of_reads[j_st].begin();
  uint64_t curr_read_start_coord = *it_start;
  std::vector<Row> curr_read_trace;
  while (it_start != coords_st.end() && it_end != ends_of_reads[j_st].end
        ()) {
    curr_read_trace.clear();
    curr_read_start_coord = *it_start;
    bool contains_input_row = false;
    uint64_t input_row_coord_in_read = 0;
    for (uint64_t cur_read_coord_ind = curr_read_start_coord;
         cur_read_coord_ind <= *it_end; ++cur_read_coord_ind) {
      if (reconstructed_paths[j_st][cur_read_coord_ind] == i) {
        contains_input_row = true;
        input_row_coord_in_read = cur_read_coord_ind;
      }
    }
    curr_read_trace.push_back(reconstructed_paths[j_st][
      cur_read_coord_ind]);
  }
  if (contains_input_row && !
      start_coords_of_already_reconstructed_reads[j_st].count(
        curr_read_start_coord)) {
    result.push_back(std::make_tuple(curr_read_trace, j_st,
      input_row_coord_in_read - curr_read_start_coord));
    reconstructed_reads[j_st].push_back(std::make_tuple(curr_read_trace
      , curr_read_start_coord, *it_end));
  }
}

```

```
    }  
    it_start++;  
    it_end++;  
  }  
}  
return result;  
}
```